

AI-Empowered Multivariate Probabilistic Forecasting: A Key Enabler for Sustainability in Open RAN

Vaishnavi Kasuluru, Luis Blanco, Cristian J. Vaca-Rubio, *Member, IEEE*, Engin Zeydan, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Albert Bel

Abstract—This paper explores the role of multivariate probabilistic forecasting in improving O-RAN operations, focusing on network sustainability aspects. A comprehensive analysis of its potential benefits and challenges, as well as its integration into the O-RAN architecture are described. The paper first presents an overview of the O-RAN architecture and components, followed by an examination of power consumption models relevant to O-RAN deployments and the challenges associated with traditional deterministic models in resource allocation. We then examine the performance of several state-of-the-art probabilistic multivariate forecasting techniques namely, Gaussian Process Vector Autoregression (GPVAR), Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) and non-probabilistic multivariate technique namely, Multivariate Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) and explain their implementation details and provide their evaluations. The simulation results show the effectiveness of these techniques in predicting Physical Resource Block (PRB) utilization and optimizing resource allocation. In particular, significant energy savings – around 20-30% – are achieved, depending on the percentile of the used probabilistic forecasting techniques. The benefits of considering probabilistic forecasting techniques compared to multi-variate LSTM are also analyzed. Our results emphasize the potential of probabilistic forecasting to improve energy efficiency and sustainability in O-RAN operations.

Index Terms—Sustainability, Open RAN, 6G, Probabilistic Forecasting, Network Analytics, Artificial Intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of mobile technologies has led to significant advances in network infrastructure, culminating in the development of Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architectures [1]. O-RAN represents a transformative approach to mobile networks, characterized by its openness, flexibility and vendor neutrality. This new paradigm aims to disaggregate network components, promote interoperability and drive innovation to ultimately improve the efficiency and adaptability of mobile networks. As we move into the 6G era, the efficient management and optimization of O-RAN operations has become a critical challenge to overcome. In addition to the disag-

gregation of network components, O-RAN promotes the use of cloud-native technologies and principles [2]. This includes the provision of network functions as containerized microservices on cloud platforms, which improves scalability, agility and resilience. Cloud-native deployments enable dynamic orchestration and automation of network functions, enabling rapid provisioning, scaling and optimization in response to changing network requirements. One of the key benefits of O-RAN is the support of advanced network intelligence and automation through the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). The RIC is a central control entity that uses Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to optimize network operations in real time [3].

The introduction of these intelligent and automated functions in O-RAN requires the development of sophisticated forecasting and optimization techniques. Traditional deterministic models are inadequate in this dynamic and complex environment, where network conditions and user demands can vary significantly and unpredictably. Probabilistic forecasting techniques, which incorporate uncertainty and variability into their models, offer a more robust solution. These techniques can predict a range of possible outcomes and their associated probabilities, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of future network conditions and more informed decision making. Probabilistic forecasting techniques can be particularly useful in optimizing resource allocation in O-RAN [4]. Accurate predictions of resource requirements, such as the utilization of radio (e.g., Physical Resource Block (PRB)) and/or computational resources, are crucial for efficient network operation. Over-utilization of resources can lead to unnecessary costs and energy consumption, while under-provisioning can impact performance and user experience. With more accurate and reliable forecasts, probabilistic models can help operators find a balance between these extremes, optimizing resource usage and improving network performance. In addition, the integration of probabilistic forecasting with the RIC can enable proactive and adaptive network management. For example, the near-RT RIC can use probabilistic forecasts to dynamically adjust resource allocation in response to network conditions in real time, while the non-RT RIC can use long-term forecasts to optimize policy and strategic decisions. This holistic approach to network management can significantly improve the efficiency, reliability and sustainability of O-RAN deployments [5].

The exponential growth of Information and Communica-

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Barcelona, 08860 Spain e-mail: {vkasuluru, lblanco, cvaca, ezeydan, abel}@cttc.es.

This work is part of the project SOFIA PID2023-147305OB-C32 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by FEDER/UE and is supported in part by the UNITY-6G project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101192650, and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). It is also supported by the Spanish MINECO – Program UNICO I+D (grants TSI-063000-2021-54 and TSI-063000-2021-55), funded by MINECO through the “NextGenerationEU” program.

tion Technologies (ICT) has led to significant advancements in global connectivity and economic development. However, this growth has also resulted in substantial GreenHouse Gas (GHG) emissions and increased power consumption. The ICT sector, encompassing data centers, network infrastructure, and end-user devices, is a significant contributor to global GHG emissions. By 2020, the ICT sector was responsible for approximately 2-4% of global carbon emissions [6] [7] with projections indicating potential growth to 14% by 2040 if current trends continue. In 2020, the carbon footprint of the ICT sector was estimated to be 763 million metric tons (Mt) of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e), an increase from 620 Mt of CO₂e in 2007 [8]. In the same period, the electricity consumption during the use stage provoked by the ICT sector escalated from 710 TWh in 2007 to 915 TWh in 2020. According to recent predictions in [9], by the year 2030, ICT networks could consume up to 21% of the world's energy. Bearing in mind all the aforementioned data, it becomes obvious that sustainable 6G network design and implementation are critical aspects to mitigate the environmental impact of ICT activities.

In mobile networks, the Radio Access Network (RAN) is a significant consumer of energy, accounting for approximately 73% of the total network energy consumption [10]. This high energy usage is primarily due to the extensive infrastructure required to maintain seamless connectivity and high data throughput. In comparison, the core network consumes 13% of the energy, data centers consume 9%, and other operations account for the remaining 5%. Consequently, reducing RAN energy consumption is crucial for enhancing the sustainability of mobile networks, lowering operational costs, and mitigating environmental impacts. Advanced techniques such as energy-efficient hardware and intelligent network management need to be explored to address this challenge.

A. Related Work

Energy efficiency in mobile networks has attracted the attention of telecom industry stakeholders, including vendors and Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), academia and standardization bodies. Significant efforts have recently been made by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) to develop unified mechanisms that offer MNOs substantial energy savings in their networks. These efforts are further supported by the O-RAN Alliance, which considers 3 potential use cases [11] i) Carrier and cell switch off; ii) RF channel switch off/on; iii) Advanced sleep mode. This paper is focused on the first use case. Cell switch off feature in O-RAN needs to be enabled by the non-real-time RIC, due to timescale of the operation and aims to reduce RAN (i.e., O-CU/DU/RU) power consumption by switching cells on/off. AI/ML-assisted solutions in the Non-RT RIC manage traffic load and automate the decision to switch carriers or cells on/off using O1 and/or Open fronthaul M-plane parameters.

Mobile network deployments usually involve capacity base cells co-located together with coverage cells. Coverage cells are designed to maximize the geographical area covered by the network, ensuring that users have a consistent and reliable signal wherever they go. Capacity cells, on the other hand, are

designed to handle a high volume of traffic and provide high data rates in hot spot, densely populated areas (e.g., shopping malls, technopoles). Within this context, the variation in traffic load in mobile networks, driven by users' mobility and behavior patterns, creates a strong motivation for implementing cell switch on/off operations in the Radio Access Network (RAN). During working weekdays, urban areas experience high traffic loads due to a concentration of people in offices and commercial zones, while suburban areas have low traffic loads as most residents are away at work. Conversely, in the evenings and on weekends, traffic shifts towards suburban areas as people return home. By dynamically adjusting the active cells based on real-time traffic demands, network resources can be utilized more efficiently. During low-traffic periods, certain cells can be switched off, reducing unnecessary resource usage and providing significant energy savings. References [12] and [10] are excellent surveys on sustainable technologies and energy efficient approaches for Radio Access Networks, including key enablers such as massive MIMO, lean carrier design or advanced idle modes. All the techniques can be classified into three categories: time domain, antenna domain or carrier-domain. Base station on/off switching fall into the first category. Several cell on/off switching algorithms have been proposed in the literature, e.g., [13], based on traditional optimization methods, which consider just the traffic load or the number of user equipments attached. Other approaches, such as [14], rely on more advanced techniques and consider ML algorithms, such as reinforcement learning for base station deactivation in massive-MIMO networks, hence, not relying in an O-RAN architecture.

Data-driven techniques have been recently considered for network traffic or resource prediction [15] [16]. Nevertheless, as pointed out in reference [12], there is currently a limited understanding of how traffic prediction errors, including forecasting inaccuracies or uncertainties, could affect power-saving strategies. Furthermore, it is often challenging to determine how improvements in the prediction of network traffic and/or resources could help in minimizing the power consumption in the RAN. Nevertheless, it has been recently shown that energy/power consumption is closely related to the requested radio resources. In particular, recent research in [17] has provided a realistic characterization of 5G multi-carrier Base Stations (BSs), offering an analytical energy consumption model based on extensive data collection campaigns. In line with this study, references [18] and [17] have shown that, in modern BSs, power consumption increases linearly with the PRB load —defined as the ratio of average used PRBs in a BS to the maximum number of PRBs available at the remote unit. Furthermore, as highlighted in [19], the Downlink (DL) PRB load is the parameter that holds the highest significance in the radio unit energy consumption. Generally, BSs are designed to handle high traffic volumes during peak hours, which often results in significant underutilized bandwidth during most of the day.

The concept of probabilistic forecasting has been extensively researched in various areas such as energy production [20] or supply chain management [21]. However, its use in telecommunications, particularly in the context of O-RAN, is

still relatively little researched. Previous studies have mainly focused on single-point forecasting models that provide deterministic predictions without taking into account the uncertainties inherent in the dynamics of the network [22]. Recent research has begun to fill this gap by investigating probabilistic methods such as Bayesian networks [23], Gaussian processes [24], and deep learning-based models [25] for network parameter forecasting. Above studies have shown that probabilistic forecasting can improve the performance and reliability of networks. However, there is a need for further research and validation of these techniques specifically in the context of sustainable O-RAN, as its unique architectural and operational characteristics need to be taken into account when integrating probabilistic forecasting techniques into its framework.

B. Motivation and Contribution

Conventional strategies for resource allocation and network management often rely on deterministic models that fail to account for the inherent uncertainties and dynamic nature of modern mobile networks. Such approaches can lead to suboptimal performance, inefficient use of resources and increased operating costs. In contrast, probabilistic forecasting techniques offer a promising solution as they provide a more comprehensive understanding of network conditions and resource requirements. By incorporating uncertainty and variability into forecasting models, these techniques can significantly improve the accuracy and reliability of network analysis, enabling more informed decision making and optimized resource allocation. This paper aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on multivariate probabilistic forecasting techniques in telecommunications by focusing on its application within the O-RAN architecture. The primary contributions of this study are threefold:

- We propose a novel framework that integrates probabilistic forecasting techniques to enhance the power efficiency of O-RAN deployments. This framework utilises advanced state-of-the-art AI-based forecasting models to predict network conditions and resource requirements, and enables dynamic and adaptive resource allocation.
- We present a detailed power consumption model tailored to O-RAN environments. This model captures the energy dynamics of various network components and provides a basis for evaluating the impact of probabilistic forecasts on power efficiency.
- We conduct a thorough evaluation of several state-of-the-art multivariate forecasting techniques, including Multivariate Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM), Gaussian Process Vector Autoregression (GPVAR), and Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT). The performance of these techniques is assessed using a set of rigorous evaluation metrics, focusing on their ability to accurately predict PRB utilization and improve the sustainability of O-RAN operations by achieving power-saving between 11.25% to 30.58%. Probabilistic models like GPVAR and TFT showcased superior performance with lowest values of MAE around 8.26 and 8.52, respectively, MAPE of 25.48 and 35.96, respectively, normalized deviation of around

0.159 and 0.167, CRPS of 0.55 and 0.75 respectively and many more.

The rest of the paper is organized as follow: Section II presents the problem statement, outlining the challenges associated with resource allocation and power efficiency in O-RAN and describes the power-efficient O-RAN framework and the architecture design with its key components and operational principles. Section III formulates the power consumption model used in this paper. In Section IV, we describe the evaluated multivariate forecasting techniques, including their theoretical foundations and implementation details. Section V presents the proposed method to achieve power saving in the O-RAN. Section VI presents the simulation results, highlighting the performance of the forecasting techniques in predicting PRB utilization and assessing the sustainability of O-RAN operations. Finally, Section VII summarizes the main findings and discusses possible directions for future research.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND PROPOSED O-RAN FRAMEWORK

A. Problem Definition

In our scenario, we have different Open-Radio Unit (O-RU)s serving an area, that we refer to as *capacity* and *coverage* base stations. These base station are responsible for serving the users by allocating PRBs to handle the aggregated data traffic in the O-RAN network. The capacity base station is designed to handle high data traffic in areas with high user density and usually has fewer PRBs than a coverage base station. It is used to offload traffic from the coverage base station during peak demand periods, which usually have some seasonality along certain times of the day or days of the week. The coverage base station for network coverage, on the other hand, is designed to cover a larger area and has a higher capacity of PRBs so that it can serve a higher volume of traffic. This ensures continuous availability of services when the capacity base station is switched off. Figure 1 illustrates the scenario depicted. The aim is to predict the future demand for PRBs at both capacity and coverage base stations, as well as the summation when all PRBs (i.e. capacity + coverage) are served by coverage. These predictions will help in determining the optimal times to switch off the capacity base station and let the coverage base station handle all the traffic when ensuring it does not exceed its total available PRBs. Such a strategy is crucial for energy savings and efficient use of resources, taking advantage of seasonal trends in traffic at different times.

Formally, we depict the multivariate PRB allocation forecasting problem as a time series¹ by $\mathbf{y}_t \in \mathbb{R}^N$ at time t , then our goal is to model the joint conditional distribution

$$P(\mathbf{y}_{t_0:T} | \mathbf{y}_{1:t_0-1}) \quad (1)$$

of the future of each PRB allocation value in the multivariate time series $[\mathbf{y}_{t_0}, \mathbf{y}_{t_0+1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_T] := \mathbf{y}_{t_0:T}$ given its past

¹In our specific use case, without loss of generality and for the sake of simplicity, we considered one capacity, one coverage O-RUs collocated under the umbrella of the same RIC. Thus we set N which is total number of time series to $N = 3$ for each of the series, i.e., coverage, capacity, and summation of requested radio resources.

Fig. 1: Considered Scenario and O-RAN architecture. On the left: Scenario depiction. On the right: O-RAN architecture for sustainable radio resource allocation.

$[\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-2}, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-1}] := \mathbf{y}_{1:t_0-1}$, where t_0 denotes the time point from which we assume y_t to be unknown at prediction time. To avoid confusion, we refer to time ranges $[1, t_0 - 1]$ and $[t_0, T]$ as the conditioning and prediction ranges, respectively. Once we learn to forecast and quantify the uncertainty in the prediction range, we provide a sustainability analysis using (2). By accurately predicting PRB demand and making informed decisions on base station operation, network operators can enhance both the efficiency and sustainability of their wireless communication networks.

B. Power Efficient O-RAN Framework

The key advantage of O-RAN lies in its interoperability, openness and intelligence, enabling network operators and third-party applications to provide dynamic, intelligent and collaborative solutions to emerging real-world requirements [26]. The power-efficient O-RAN framework designed for our use case is shown in Figure 1. A sustainable radio resource demand forecasting radio App (rApp) is integrated into the management and orchestration framework [27] to accurately learn and predict radio resource requirements, which in turn contributes to power savings. The framework not only helps to reduce energy consumption, but also improves operational and network cost efficiency through reduced resource waste and a greener wireless network. Joint resource management and sustainable network provisioning with the ability to make dynamic and real-time adjustments represent a significant improvement in mobile network automation [28].

Figure 1 is divided into two segments, with the network scenario on the left and the O-RAN architecture on the right. In our work, we consider an environment equipped with two types of base stations (O-RUs): coverage base stations and capacity base stations, shown in cyan-green and violet circles, respectively. The coverage base stations provide a broader spectrum coverage area as they serve a large number of

User Equipment (UE)s, smart homes, Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) and other Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices. However, the capacity base stations aim to handle higher data rates, UEs and other devices in a small localized region such as nearby shopping malls, stadiums, offices, etc. The scenario illustrates the diverse and distributed nature of mobile networks. O-RUs serve as radio access points that connect the UEs to the core network. They are responsible for transmitting and receiving radio signals to and from the UEs for efficient wireless communication [27]. They are connected to Open-Distributed Unit (O-DU)s via open fronthaul planes. The cooperation and connectivity between these elements is essential for sustainable and efficient resource management. The O-RAN architecture on the right side of Figure 1 includes several important components, such as O-DU, Open-Central Unit-Control Plane (O-CU-CP), Open-Central Unit-User Plane (O-CU-UP), Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (RT RIC), Non-RT RIC and Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) [29]. O-DU and Open-Central Unit (O-CU) are the core components of O-RAN, which are connected to RICs via various open interfaces. The functions of O-RU, O-CU and O-DU are similar to the disaggregated 5G RAN according to the 3GPP specifications, with additional support for interfaces and specification of O-RAN [5]. They enable seamless network communication by effectively managing scheduling, data processing and control functions.

The Non-RT RIC [28] is responsible for optimizing and managing the network using intelligent AI/ML models and coarse grained data. Multiple rApps with latency requirements higher than 1sec can be simultaneously run in the Near-RT RIC platform. They communicate with other components in O-RAN via the interfaces A1, O1 and O2. Specifically for our use case, a sustainable resource demand forecasting rApp is considered to collect and process allocated DL PRB data to multiple O-RUs via Near-RT RIC using three elements as shown in Figure 1: a monitoring system, an analytical

engine, and a decision engine. The monitoring system receives historical PRB data from data gathering eXtended application (xApp) in Near-RT RIC and forwards it to the analytic engine. In the analytic engine, the data is preprocessed and divided into training and test sets for forecasting the PRB requirements using probabilistic AI/ML models, such as GPVAR and TFT. Then the predicted range of PRBs is passed to the decision engine, which uses these predicted PRB values to decide whether to switch the capacity base station ON or OFF. Near-RT RIC is equipped with the time-sensitive xApps, which require a latency of 10 ms to 1 s [29]. The two main xApps that support the use case of creating a sustainable provision of resources are the *data gathering xApp* and the *O-RU ON/OFF Actuator xApp*. The data gathering xApp collects the allocated history DL PRB information from O-DU. In addition, the O-RU ON/OFF Actuator xApp becomes responsible for executing the ON/OFF decision of O-RU (capacity base station) received from the decision engine of resource demand forecasting rApp in the disaggregated RAN in real time. In summary, the overall architecture promotes a sustainable and energy-efficient O-RAN ecosystem by ensuring efficient radio resource allocation with optimized power consumption.

III. POWER CONSUMPTION MODEL

Consider the power consumption model for 5G Base stations (BS) recently introduced in [17], [30]. The total power consumption, denoted by P_T , can be mathematically characterized as follows:

$$P_T = P_0 + P_{BB} + P_{Tran} + P_{PA} + P_{out}, \quad (2)$$

where P_0 represents the baseline power consumption in sleep mode, P_{BB} denotes the baseband processing power consumption, P_{Tran} represents the power consumption by the RF chains, P_{PA} indicates the static consumption of the power amplifier, and P_{out} corresponds to the power required for data transmission. The initial terms, i.e., P_0 , P_{BB} , P_{Tran} , and P_{PA} are dependent on the number of available and active RF chains. P_{Tran} is the product between the number of RF chains, denoted by M_{av} and the power consumed by each RF chain, denoted as D_{Tran} . For the sake of simplicity and without a loss of generality, herein we assume one transceiver. Similarly, the term P_{PA} is given by the product of the number of RF chains and the static power consumed by each multi-carrier power amplifier D_{PA} :

$$\begin{aligned} P_{Tran} &= M_{av} D_{Tran} \\ P_{PA} &= M_{av} D_{PA}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The last term in (2) P_{out} is proportional to the transmitted traffic volume:

$$P_{out} = \frac{1}{\eta} P_{TX} \frac{R_{BS}}{C_{BS}}, \quad (4)$$

where η denote the efficiency of the power amplifiers, and P_{TX} represent the maximum transmit power. The symbols R_{BS} and C_{BS} denote the actual rate and the capacity of the base station, respectively. The total capacity of the base station can

be calculated using the classical Shannon-Hartley theorem, which is expressed as follows:

$$C = B \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}). \quad (5)$$

Considering the capacity formula, it is evident that P_{out} in (4) is inversely proportional to the total bandwidth in the O-RU. A surrogate for $\frac{R_{BS}}{C_{BS}}$ in (4) is the DL PRB load, defined as the ratio between the average number of DL PRBs and the maximum number of DL PRBs available. Recent studies in [19] and [18] have demonstrated that the DL PRB load is the most significant feature in modeling radio unit power consumption. Additionally, it is important to note that the transmit power increases linearly with the number of used PRBs [17]. Consequently, there is a trade-off between meeting the DL PRB resource demands and minimizing energy consumption.

IV. MULTIVARIATE FORECASTING TECHNIQUES

Multivariate forecasting techniques are used to predict future radio resource demands (e.g. PRBs) for both capacity and coverage cells by considering several influencing factors simultaneously. In contrast to univariate methods [31], which rely solely on past values of the target variable, multivariate techniques incorporate a variety of relevant features such as historical PRB usage, time of day, day of week, etc. In our work, we input the PRB time series of capacity, coverage and summation as relevant features. This enables the modeling of complex relationships and interactions between the different PRBs demands, leading to more accurate and robust predictions. To this end, we will introduce the multivariate LSTM as a single-point baseline, i.e. there is no uncertainty prediction, and compare it with two major probabilistic forecasting methods to solve the problem in (1): GPVAR [32], and TFT [33].

A. Multivariate LSTM

As introduced in Section II-A, without loss of generality, we consider the three PRB allocation time series in the conditioning range as a multivariate time series $\mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{y}_t\}_{t=1}^{t_0-1}$, where $\mathbf{y}_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the observations at time t across the three time series (capacity, coverage, and summation). The objective is to predict the future values of this multivariate PRB demand $\mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{y}_t\}_{t=t_0}^T$ in the prediction range. The LSTM network is characterized by its ability to maintain long-term dependencies through its cell state \mathbf{c}_t and hidden state \mathbf{h}_t . The key components of an LSTM cell at time t are defined as follows:

1) *Input gate*:

$$\mathbf{i}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_i \mathbf{y}_t + \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_i) \quad (6)$$

where σ denotes the sigmoid function, $\mathbf{W}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbf{U}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, and $\mathbf{b}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the weight matrices and bias vector for the input gate.

2) *Forget gate*:

$$\mathbf{f}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_f \mathbf{y}_t + \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_f) \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_f \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbf{U}_f \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, and $\mathbf{b}_f \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the weight matrices and bias vector for the forget gate.

3) *Cell state update:*

$$\tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_c \mathbf{y}_t + \mathbf{U}_c \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_c) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbf{U}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, and $\mathbf{b}_c \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the weight matrices and bias vector for the cell state update. The actual cell state is then updated as:

$$\mathbf{c}_t = \mathbf{f}_t \odot \mathbf{c}_{t-1} + \mathbf{i}_t \odot \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t \quad (9)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication.

4) *Output gate:*

$$\mathbf{o}_t = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_o \mathbf{y}_t + \mathbf{U}_o \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_o) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbf{U}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, and $\mathbf{b}_o \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the weight matrices and bias vector for the output gate.

5) *Hidden state:*

$$\mathbf{h}_t = \mathbf{o}_t \odot \tanh(\mathbf{c}_t) \quad (11)$$

6) *Training with Backpropagation Through Time (BPTT):*

To train the LSTM network, we utilize the Backpropagation Through Time (BPTT) algorithm. The loss function \mathcal{L} we use is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{T - t_0} \sum_{t=t_0}^T \|\mathbf{y}_t - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_t\| \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t$ is the predicted value of \mathbf{y}_t . The gradients of the loss function with respect to the network parameters θ are computed using the chain rule, propagated backwards through time.

B. GPVAR

We here contextualize our problem using GPVAR. Let us denote the values of the PRB multivariate time series by $y_{i,t}$, where $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ indexes the individual univariate component time series (capacity, coverage, and summation), and t indexes time. We will denote the multivariate observation vector at time t by \mathbf{y}_t . Given $t_0 - 1$ observations $\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-1}$, we are interested in forecasting the future values from t_0 up to T , i.e., we want to estimate the joint conditional distribution (1). In this way, this model takes the form of a non-linear, deterministic state space model whose state $\mathbf{h}_{i,t} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ evolves independently for each time series i according to transition dynamics φ ,

$$\mathbf{h}_{i,t} = \varphi_{\theta_h}(\mathbf{h}_{i,t-1}, y_{i,t-1}) \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad (13)$$

where the transition dynamics φ are parametrized using a LSTM [34]. Note that the LSTM is applied for each time series separately, but parameters θ_h are shared for all the time series. Given the state values $\mathbf{h}_{i,t}$ for all time series $i = 1, 2, 3$ and denoting by \mathbf{h}_t the collection of state values for all series at time t , we parametrize the joint distribution using a Gaussian copula [35],

$$p(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{h}_t) = \mathcal{N}([f_1(y_{1,t}), f_2(y_{2,t}), f_3(y_{3,t})]^T | \mu(\mathbf{h}_t), \Sigma(\mathbf{h}_t)). \quad (14)$$

The transformations $f_i : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ here are invertible mappings of the form $\Phi^{-1} \circ \hat{F}_i$, where Φ denotes the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution, and

\hat{F}_i denotes an estimate of the marginal distribution of the i -th time series $y_{i,1}, \dots, y_{i,t_0-1}$. The role of these functions f_i is to transform the data for the i -th time series such that marginally it follows a standard normal distribution. The functions $\mu(\cdot)$ and $\Sigma(\cdot)$ map the state \mathbf{h}_t to the mean and covariance of a Gaussian distribution over the transformed observations².

Under this model, we can factorize the joint distribution of the observations as

$$p(\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_T) = \prod_{t=1}^T p(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t-1}) = \prod_{t=1}^T p(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{h}_t). \quad (15)$$

Both the state update function φ and the mappings $\mu(\cdot)$ and $\Sigma(\cdot)$ have free parameters that are learned from the data. We denote θ the vector of all free parameters, consisting of the parameters of the state update θ_h as well as θ_μ and θ_Σ which denote the free parameters in $\mu(\cdot)$ and $\Sigma(\cdot)$. Given θ and \mathbf{h}_{t_0} , we can produce Monte Carlo samples from the joint predictive distribution

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{y}_{t_0}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_T | \mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-1}) \\ = p(\mathbf{y}_{t_0}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_T | \mathbf{h}_{t_0}) \\ = \prod_{t=t_0}^T p(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{h}_t) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

by sequentially sampling from $P(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{h}_t)$ and updating \mathbf{h}_t using φ . We learn the parameters θ from the observed data $\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-1}$ using maximum likelihood estimation i.e., by minimizing the loss function

$$-\log p(\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-1}) = - \sum_{t=1}^{t_0-1} \log p(\mathbf{y}_t | \mathbf{h}_t), \quad (17)$$

using gradient descent-based optimization.

C. TFT

We also evaluate TFT for forecasting future PRB demand in a high-dimensional multivariate setting. The TFT utilises attention mechanisms and quantile loss to produce accurate and probabilistic multi-horizon forecasts [33]. We also investigate TFTs to capture complex temporal dependencies and quantify prediction uncertainty. Let us denote the values of the PRB multivariate time series by $y_{i,t}$, where $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ indexes the individual univariate component time series (capacity, coverage, and summation), and t indexes time. We will denote the multivariate observation vector at time t by \mathbf{y}_t . Given $t_0 - 1$ observations $\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{t_0-1}$, we are interested in forecasting the future values from t_0 up to T , i.e., we want to estimate the joint conditional distribution (1). Let us denote the amount of time steps in the prediction horizon as τ . To enhance the forecast, TFTs include additional input features denominated as *unknown* $z_{i,t}$, *known* $x_{i,t}$, and static covariates s_i which provide contextual metadata about measured entities that does not depend on time. TFTs output prediction intervals via

²We gently refer the readers to [32] for a detailed description of the obtention of $\mu(\cdot)$, and $\Sigma(\cdot)$.

quantiles. Each quantile q forecast of τ -step-ahead at time t is given by:

$$\hat{y}_i(q, t, \tau) = f_q(\tau, y_{i,1:t_0-1}, z_{i,1:t_0-1}, x_{i,1:T}, s_i), \quad (18)$$

where $y_{i,1:t_0-1}$ denotes the values in the conditioning range, $z_{i,1:t_0-1}$ the unknown, $x_{i,1:T}$ known, and s_i static covariates. Note that the unknown features are not defined in the prediction range while the known features are. The static covariates represent extra information that does not vary with time. In our specific problem, we do not use covariates nor unknown features, but we do use known features such as the day and hours in the future to forecast. The TFT architecture comprises different components to provide a high forecasting performance. The most significant components of TFTs are³:

- *Gating mechanisms*: TFT employs gating mechanisms to dynamically adjust the complexity. This adaptability allows the model to skip over unused components, optimizing depth and network complexity according to the specific dataset and forecasting scenario. By adjusting its internal structure, TFT efficiently manages computational resources and enhances performance across diverse datasets.
- *Variable selection networks*: The variable selection networks in TFT are crucial for identifying and focusing on relevant input variables at each time step. This component dynamically selects which features are most pertinent for the current prediction, ensuring that the model remains focused on the most impactful information and reducing the influence of irrelevant or noisy data.
- *Static covariate encoders*: TFT integrates static features through its static covariate encoders. These encoders generate context vectors that encode static features, such as static metadata or features that do not change over time, into the network. This encoding helps to condition the temporal dynamics of the model, allowing the network to incorporate stable context information into its predictions.
- *Temporal processing*: To capture both short-term and long-term temporal dependencies, TFT incorporates advanced temporal processing mechanisms. It uses a sequence-to-sequence layer to handle local, short-term temporal relationships, while a novel interpretable multi-head attention block is utilized to model long-term dependencies. This dual approach ensures that the model effectively learns and integrates both immediate and extended temporal patterns from observed and known time-varying inputs.
- *Prediction intervals via quantile forecasts*: TFT generates prediction intervals using quantile forecasts. This feature allows the model to estimate a range of possible target values for each prediction horizon, providing a measure of uncertainty and confidence in the forecasts.

To train our TFT, we optimize the quantile loss function for a given quantile q which is given by:

$$L_q(y_t, \hat{y}_t^q) = \begin{cases} q(y_t - \hat{y}_t^q) & \text{if } y_t > \hat{y}_t^q \\ (1-q)(\hat{y}_t^q - y_t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

³We gently refer the readers to [33] for a more detailed explanation.

where y_t is the true value at time t and \hat{y}_t^q is the predicted quantile value at time t . The total quantile loss for all quantiles and time steps is:

$$L = \frac{1}{|Q|} \sum_{q \in Q} \sum_{t=t_0}^T L_q(y_t, \hat{y}_t^q), \quad (20)$$

where $|Q|$ is the number of quantiles and t_0 to T represents the range of time steps in the prediction range.

D. Evaluation Metrics

Error metrics play a crucial role in quantifying and validating the performance of forecasting models. They help assess the consistency of predictions with actual PRB historical data. A deeper understanding of error metrics is important to make efficient estimator selection decisions. In addition, the accuracy and reliability of estimators can be revealed, which simplifies model comparison and contributes to robust decision making [28]. In this paper, error metrics such as Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Normalized Deviation (ND), Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS), coverage and quantile loss are used to calibrate and analyze the forecasting estimators. As mentioned before, let the values of PRB allocation multivariate time series (capacity, coverage, and summation/Total PRB demand) be $y_{i,t}$, where $y_{i,t} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the PRB test instances at time t across the 3 time series $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. The error metrics are calculated between the actual and predicted PRB estimates for each individual time series. For ease of understanding, let us consider only the first time series $y_{i,t}$. Furthermore the prediction of $y_{i,t}$ are range of PRBs which equals to $[\hat{y}_{i,t_0}, \hat{y}_{i,t_1}, \dots, \hat{y}_{i,T}]$.

Basic error metrics like MSE, MAE, and MAPE are widely used metrics for single-point forecast models like LSTM [4]. In the case of probabilistic estimators, the achieved prediction $\hat{y}_{i,t}$ at every time instance t , is a column vector ranging from $[\hat{y}_{i,t}^1, \hat{y}_{i,t}^2, \dots, \hat{y}_{i,t}^q]^T$ with q being the percentiles ranging from 1-th to 99-th and $t = t_0 \dots T$. To make a fair comparison between LSTM and other probabilistic estimators, only MSE, MAE, and MAPE are used [4]. Joint metrics⁴ for both single-point forecast and probabilistic forecasting are described as follows:

- **Mean Square Error (MSE)**: Provides an average of the squared difference between actual and predicted PRBs [4].

$$MSE = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=t_0}^T |y_{i,t} - \hat{y}_{i,t}|^2 \quad (21)$$

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE)**: Measures the average error magnitude in set of forecasts. The over and under-estimations are treated equally while calculating MAE, making it less sensitive to outliers [4].

$$MAE = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=t_0}^T |y_{i,t} - \hat{y}_{i,t}| \quad (22)$$

⁴For probabilistic methods, MSE, MAE and MAPE are computed considering the median of the probabilistic forecasts.

- **Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):** Computes the difference between actual and forecasted PRBs in terms of percentage [4]. They are useful when handling datasets of varying scales or different contexts.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=t_0}^T \frac{|y_{i,t} - \hat{y}_{i,t}|}{|y_{i,t}|} \quad (23)$$

Only probabilistic forecasting metrics are described as follows:

- **Normalized Deviation (ND):** This metric helps in accessing the accuracy of forecast models. The average deviation between the forecasted and actual values is normalized by the range of the actual values to compute ND [36]. Prediction accuracy is considered high if the ND is low.

$$ND = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=t_0}^T \frac{|y_{i,t} - \hat{y}_{i,t}|}{\text{mean}(y_i)} \quad (24)$$

- **Coverage:** Calculates the proportion of actual values that fall within the predicted interval. For example, Let us consider a 99% prediction interval; then, 99% of true PRB values are expected to fall within or below the specified interval. In general, the forecasting model's uncertainty and data spread are efficiently inferred from this metric [37].

$$Coverage = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=t_0}^T 1(y_{i,t} \in \hat{y}_{i,t}) \quad (25)$$

- **Quantile Loss (QL):** Average difference between predicted and actual PRBs at particular quantile q is computed here. It is commonly used to evaluate forecasts in applications where quantile-based prediction accuracy is important [36].

$$QL = \begin{cases} (y_{i,t} - \hat{y}_{i,t}) \cdot q, & \text{if } y_{i,t} \geq \hat{y}_{i,t} \\ (\hat{y}_{i,t} - y_{i,t}) \cdot (1 - q), & \text{if } y_{i,t} < \hat{y}_{i,t} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

- **Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS):** This scoring rule is used to assess the estimator's accuracy and sharpness more precisely. The difference in Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of predictions and empirical CDF of true values is calculated in CRPS. It measures how far the predictions are from the actual PRBs over all possible values [38]. Let \mathcal{F} be the forecast distribution.

$$CRPS(\mathcal{F}, y_{i,t}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\mathcal{F}(\hat{y}_{i,t}) - 1(\hat{y}_{i,t} \geq y_{i,t}))^2 dy \quad (27)$$

V. PROPOSED POWER SAVING ALGORITHM FOR O-RAN

This section focuses on achieving power savings in O-RAN using advanced probabilistic forecasting models such as GPVAR and TFT as well as multivariate LSTM, which serve as a baseline model for benchmarking. It is assumed that the estimators are integrated into the O-RAN RIC controller. Effective and dynamic resource allocation is important for

efficient power consumption without wasting resources. The accurately predicted PRBs in turn help in designing an efficient strategy to switch off the capacity base station depending on the resource utilisation. The two significant conditions to be satisfied for switching off the base station are:

1. Capacity base stations forecast PRB demand at a particular time should be less than a predefined threshold.
2. The total PRB demand (PRB required for capacity + coverage base station) predicted at a specific time instance should not be above the maximum PRBs that a coverage station can offer without any bottlenecks.

Effective power usage is ensured through condition one by switching off the underutilized capacity base station while the service quality degradation is prevented by condition 2 through ensuring that the coverage base station can handle the combined load requirements.

Fig. 2: Comprehensive workflow for achieving power saving in O-RAN.

Figure 2 shows a detailed explanation of the solution implemented to achieve a sustainable O-RAN. It starts with the gathering of historical data on allocated PRBs from different base stations in xApp via O-DU. The gathered historical data is shared with resource forecasting rApp for further processing. Next, the analytical engine in rApp trains the forecasting estimators using the input PRB allocation information, followed by the prediction of future PRB demands using the trained

models. The decision engine uses these predictions to check whether conditions 1 and 2 are met. The fulfilment of both conditions guarantees that the capacity base station can be switched off and that the coverage station can handle all service requests from users in that particular area without overhead. If this is not the case, the capacity station is active and the total power consumption is higher, which results in no or low power savings. To calculate the power consumption and the corresponding power savings, the parameters of the power consumption model explained in Section III are initialized with values as explained in the reference [18]. Finally, the decision is implemented by the actuator xApp within the O-RAN framework. The process includes continuous monitoring and decision adjustment for efficient network operation and increased energy savings. This approach helps to achieve a better balance between resource utilisation and power efficiency, which is important for a sustainable O-RAN.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section presents an analysis of the performance of deterministic and probabilistic multivariate forecast models. Python is the primary programming language used to develop the estimators within the rApp framework. The DL requested PRBs for the next 48 hours are predicted using various estimators, namely multivariate LSTM, GPVAR, and TFT. The data is split into a 70:30 ratio, where training and validation are performed using 70 percent of available PRB data, and the remaining 30 percent is used for model evaluation. In this study, approximately one month of PRB data was used for model training, which in turn aided in capturing realistic temporal variations in network load. The DL PRB history data can be obtained from O-DU via the O1 interface in O-RAN.

The dataset used in this work was generated by simulating traffic and mobility patterns for different numbers of end users in a realistic urban environment [39]. The authors of [39] considered a city-wide RAN scenario for traffic simulation and recorded user behavior across 50 base stations. Mobility patterns of 15,000 users were simulated, evenly distributed across enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC), and massive machine-type communication (mMTC) slices, reflecting the classic use cases of modern RAN deployment [39]. Moreover, to ensure realistic traffic dynamics and mobility patterns, a highly populated geographical region of Milan, Italy, was considered [39]. The dataset contains detailed information about PRB allocations, slice-specific traffic demand, SLA violations, and network conditions. The PRB data plays a crucial role in evaluating the performance of probabilistic forecasting techniques and resource provisioning, as it effectively captures the dynamic nature of network load in real time. For this work, we considered the PRB data of only 2 base stations: Coverage base station and capacity base station.

The multivariate LSTM model is designed with the Keras library. The LSTM network is trained for 41 epochs with 3 dense layers, 10 hidden layers, 0.5 dropouts, Adam optimizer and l2 regularizer. The learning rate is adjusted based on the validation loss. The probabilistic estimators GPVAR and TFT

are then modeled using the Pytorch library. The parameters used for these probabilistic estimators are batch size, maximum epochs, prediction length and hidden size, which are set to 128, 50, 48 hours and 100, respectively. The context length is considered to be 120 hours (5 days). In order to improve the understanding of data trends and patterns through estimators, the additional time-related variables such as hours, weekdays and weekends are passed as parameters to time-varying known reals when creating data loaders. In the case of GPVAR, 2 Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) layers are used with multivariate normal distribution loss, Adam optimizer, and learning rate of 0.01. TFTs are operated with a learning rate of 0.03 with quantile loss and ranger optimizer. The optimum learning rate for both cases is determined by the tuner module. Overfitting is prevented by tuning the learning rate and using an early stopping strategy.

In this study, it is assumed that two types of base stations are available as mentioned before, namely coverage and capacity base stations, which are the first two input time series for the analysis. Total PRB demand, which is the sum of the actual PRB demand of coverage and capacity cells, forms the third time series. Accurately predicting and analyzing the required PRBs ensure the user's quality of service requirements are met through efficient network operation. The maximum PRBs available at the coverage base station is 140 PRBs, and the capacity of the base station is 75 PRBs. These configurations play an important role in determining the upper limit of resource allocation for extended or concentrated areas to ensure that the networks can handle a significant traffic load and maintain efficient operation without excessive power usage.

A. Multivariate PRB Forecasting Assessment

This section analyses the performance of the different estimators in predicting future PRB requirements in terms of error metrics and over/under estimation percentage. Figure 3 compares the performance of the LSTM and the GPVAR estimator for predicting the PRB requirement of the coverage base station, the capacity base station and the total PRB demands in three different subplots. The true observations are shown in blue with LSTM based predictions in orange. The prediction range of the GPVAR estimator is in green shade, and its median value is highlighted in purple. In particular, the shaded areas show the 50% and 90% prediction interval. Looking at all 3 subplots, it can be seen that the performance has a moderate level of confidence. The GPVAR can capture the overall trend, but in some points, it can be seen that it misses the short-term variations.

Figure 4 compares the performance of the LSTM and TFT estimator similar to Figure 3. It can be seen that TFT captures the prediction trends more accurately than GPVAR due to a high confidence level during prediction and the self-attention mechanism. The prediction of TFT is more consistent with the true observations than that of LSTM. TFT proves to be more robust when performing predictions. It provides more reliable results, regardless of the configuration of the base station.

The estimation of deterministic single-point and probabilistic forecast models with regard to various performance metrics

Fig. 3: Forecast comparison of LSTM and GPVAR models for downlink PRB utilization of different Base Stations. (Shaded areas represent prediction intervals showing uncertainty.)

defined previously in Section IV-D are shown in Table I. GPVAR and TFT outperform LSTM with the lower error values of MSE, MAE, and MAPE irrespective of the base station, indicating better accuracy and efficient understanding of historical data by probabilistic models. Note that for probabilistic methods, we have considered the median for computing those metrics. For probabilistic forecasting models, we considered Normalized Deviation, CRPS, Quantile Loss, and Coverage to quantify the accuracy and quality of probabilistic predictions. It turns out that TFT performs slightly better than GPVAR, with a lower value for the normalized deviation. The lower CRPS values underline the effectiveness of the TFT model in calibrating the distribution and more accurately predicting PRB demand for all types of base stations. The quantile loss and coverage help to evaluate the performance of the estimators at different distribution points. TFT tends to perform slightly better at some percentiles, while GPVAR makes better predictions at other percentiles and thus shows a challenging performance. In terms of coverage, TFT provided more consistent coverage than GPVAR across all percentiles and base stations, indicating better closeness and calibration of predictions to actual values.

Figure 5 shows the percentages of over- and under-provisioning of PRB requests from capacity base stations at the 5-th, 25-th, 50-th, 75-th, and 99-th percentiles for GPVAR and TFT estimators. The LSTM provided over- and underestimates of 41.6 and 58.3, respectively, and has not been shown here

Fig. 4: Forecast comparison of LSTM and TFT models for downlink PRB utilization of different Base Stations. (Shaded areas represent prediction intervals showing uncertainty.)

in the plot as it provides a single-point estimate, unlike the probabilistic models, which provide a range of PRBs so that it is possible to extract the PRBs at a particular percentile. It can be seen from Figure 5 that GPVAR provides higher underestimates than TFT at lower percentile values. As the percentile increases, the percentage of underestimation of GPVAR decreases. In contrast, the performance of TFT is more balanced with a low overestimation of 61.81%, 84.03%, and 99.3% at higher percentiles.

Fig. 5: Over and Under Estimation percentage of Capacity Base Station PRB demand.

Sound knowledge of the overestimation and underestimation percentages across different percentiles, as well as the other

TABLE I: Comparison of the performance of different forecast methods under different percentile values

Forecast Models	Coverage Base Station			Capacity Base Station			Total PRB Demands		
	MSE								
LSTM	455.01			34.03			139.02		
GPVAR	114.02			10.72			185.94		
TFT	110.02			10.46			145.34		
	MAE								
LSTM	18.01			4.818			10.21		
GPVAR	8.26			2			10.11		
TFT	8.52			1.91			9.67		
	MAPE(%)								
LSTM	79.89			69.76			46.33		
GPVAR	25.48			23.73			24.91		
TFT	35.96			31.65			32.86		
	Normalized Deviation								
GPVAR	0.167			0.181			0.167		
TFT	0.172			0.173			0.159		
	CRPS								
GPVAR	2.90			0.75			3.69		
TFT	2.22			0.55			2.48		
	Percentiles								
	5-th	50-th	99-th	5-th	50-th	99-th	5-th	50-th	99-th
	Quantile Loss								
GPVAR	0.52	4.13	0.50	0.12	1.0	0.18	0.45	5.05	0.67
TFT	0.68	4.26	0.42	0.09	0.95	0.15	0.58	4.83	0.61
	Coverage								
GPVAR	0.02	0.62	1	0.02	0.58	0.95	0.02	0.64	1
TFT	0.16	0.58	0.97	0	0.68	0.95	0.1	0.6	0.97

error metrics in Table I, helps to make efficient, accurate, and reliable decisions. Overestimation causes unwanted costs and waste of resources by over-allocating resources, while underestimation reduces the quality of service and increases customer churn. Understanding the application/service requirements and the trade-offs between the different performance metrics is important for choosing the type of estimator and the respective percentile. TFT and GPVAR have several advantages. TFTs can effectively capture the temporal patterns and long-term dependencies in data through attention mechanisms. They are characterized by their scalability in processing multivariate data, which makes them more suitable for real-world applications. However, GPVAR, a Gaussian process working with the Bayesian framework, efficiently incorporates prior knowledge, tolerates the non-stationarity of data, and understands the covariate relationship within the data. It offers high interoperability and robust performance even with smaller datasets. To summarize, an accurate estimate of PRB demand helps to achieve cost-effective, sustainable, and impressive network performance.

Table II presents the comparison of three forecasting models (LSTM, GPVAR, and TFT) in terms of average MSE, MAE, MAPE, training time, prediction time, and computation complexity across varying training dataset lengths of 1 Week, 2 Weeks, and 1 Month. As the dataset length increases, all models exhibit improved accuracy but at the cost of higher training time and memory usage. The results in the table show that LSTM performs worse in prediction accuracy than the probabilistic methods GPVAR and TFT, with consistently higher MSE, MAE, and MAPE across all dataset lengths. This indicates that LSTM struggles to represent the multivariate structure and temporal dependencies in the data, while GPVAR and TFT provide substantially more accurate forecasts. TFT achieves a good performance in terms of accuracy, due to its attention-based architecture, and GPVAR also performs

Forecasting	Training Dataset Length		
	1 Week	2 Weeks	1 Month
	Average MSE		
LSTM	614.27	507.24	246.24
GPVAR	341.26	267.58	105.59
TFT	385.66	246.59	102.20
	Average MAE		
LSTM	38.78	28.49	10.50
GPVAR	33.07	19.32	5.76
TFT	38.91	18.75	5.81
	Average MAPE (%)		
LSTM	190.72	100.80	67.28
GPVAR	121.75	84.58	28.65
TFT	124.85	76.85	30.75
	Training Time (Seconds)		
LSTM	128.2	190.5	298.97
GPVAR	302.93	572.52	1084.34
TFT	222.30	567.85	996.53
	Prediction Time (Seconds)		
LSTM	1.954	2.158	2.187
GPVAR	0.356	0.348	0.385
TFT	0.179	0.186	0.194
	CPU Usage (%) (Training/Prediction)		
LSTM	14.48/42.5	14.75/41.4	14.90/42.6
GPVAR	50.46/39.1	50.54/39.52	51.42/39.64
TFT	51.42/15.24	51.30/15.32	53.45/15.53
	Memory Usage (MiB) (Training/Prediction)		
LSTM	820.4/583.64	821.5/583.94	821.7/584.24
GPVAR	824.6/560.24	914.5/560.55	934.5/560.62
TFT	795.4/559.15	841.8/560.25	874.8/559.93

TABLE II: Performance Comparison of Forecasting Models

strongly thanks to its probabilistic treatment of uncertainty and ability to model non-stationary relationships.

Regarding computational complexity, LSTM is more expensive during prediction, showing higher prediction times than

both GPVAR and TFT. While LSTM trains faster, its forward pass at inference is heavier, making probabilistic methods more efficient for real-time prediction scenarios. GPVAR and TFT therefore offer a favorable balance between accuracy and prediction cost, outperforming LSTM in both forecast quality and inference efficiency, even though they may require more resources during training. TFT is effective computationally during prediction because of the way its architecture separates training complexity from inference efficiency. Although TFT is heavier to train, due to attention layers, gating mechanisms, variable selection networks, and multi-horizon processing, TFT inference pass is streamlined and parallelizable. Once trained, the model does not need to backpropagate or update internal states over time the way recurrent models like LSTM do. Another key factor is that TFT removes the sequential dependency inherent in LSTMs. LSTM must compute predictions step-by-step through its recurrent chain, making inference inherently slower. In contrast, TFT's architecture is designed for parallel temporal processing, which reduces prediction latency dramatically. Additionally, attention blocks in TFT selectively focus on relevant time steps rather than processing the entire history, effectively reducing computational load. Together, these design choices allow TFT to achieve strong predictive accuracy while maintaining efficient and scalable prediction performance.

B. Sustainability Analysis Assessment

This section focuses on the sustainability aspects of probabilistic forecasting using the O-RAN framework. The main objective of this analysis is to calculate the achievable power savings with different probabilistic models based on the estimated PRB requirements for a single carrier use case with 64 RF chains. Performing such an in-depth analysis is crucial for an energy-efficient and sustainable network. As described in the paper [17], different normalized parameters are used to calculate the power consumption. The parameter, namely the baseline power consumption in sleep mode, denoted as P_O , is set to 0.22, and the maximum transmit power P_{TX} is set to 0.299. The power consumption of the baseband processing P_{BB} , the power consumption of the RF chains P_{Tran} , the power consumption of the power amplifiers P_{PA} , and the efficiency of the power amplifiers η are set to 0.16, 0.09408, 0.24384 and 0.4 respectively. All these power values mentioned are normalized values. The reduction in power consumption and appropriate power saving can be efficiently quantified based on power consumption, which in turn contributes to an accurate assessment of sustainability.

The crucial aspect of the sustainability analysis is the calculation of the power savings resulting from switching off the capacity base station depending on the predicted PRB requirements. The previous section, Multivariate PRB Forecasting Assessment, showcased the benefit of using probabilistic forecasting models to estimate PRB requirements accurately due to their efficient understanding of historical traffic data and current network conditions. These capabilities are critical for optimizing power consumption, as they can help decide when a particular low-traffic base station should

be deactivated or switched off to achieve greater power saving without compromising the quality of service. The capacity station is switched off on the basis of two conditions:

1. The predicted PRB demand of the capacity base station at a certain point in time falls below a certain selected threshold value ranging from 10 PRBs to 55 PRBs.
2. The predicted total PRB demand is below the maximum PRBs (140 PRBs), which is the maximum capacity of the coverage base station.

If these two conditions are met, the coverage base station alone can handle the traffic requirements without overheads or bottlenecks when the capacity base station is switched off. Furthermore, the selection of the highest threshold of 55 PRBs (i.e., 80% of maximum capacity of capacity base station) in evaluation ensures a safety margin that accounts for dynamic traffic conditions and avoids service degradations due to sudden spikes in traffic demand.

Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 present the PRB demands and the power-saving percentage over a 48-hour prediction period for different forecasting models. The subplot at the top shows the actual value and predictions of total PRBs and the capacity base station's PRB requirement. The maximum PRB coverage base station can provide is marked in brown dashed lines at 140 PRBs. The red dashed line set at 10 PRBs in Figures 5 and 7 and 55 PRBs in Figures 6 and 8 shows the capacity base station OFF threshold. The actual total PRB demand, which is the combination of capacity and coverage base station PRB needs, is represented as a black line with the start markers and its prediction using LSTM in an olive-green star-marked line. The 95% prediction interval using a probabilistic estimator is shown as a corel-red shaded area with a purple start-marked line being the median of the obtained prediction range. Furthermore, the capacity base station's true PRB values are plotted as a black line with a circle marker. The LSTM predictions are shown in an olive-green line with circle markers, and probabilistic model predictions of 95% prediction interval are showcased as a blue-shaded area accompanied by a purple circle-marked line depicting the prediction median.

The power savings achieved using various forecasting models at different percentiles can be seen in the bottom subplot of all the figures. The results achieved using the LSTM model are drawn as olive green bars, and the probabilistic model at the 2-nd, 50-th, and 98-th percentiles are represented as sky blue, purple, and steel blue bars, respectively. These bars explain the changes in the percentage of power saved at a particular percentile, namely 2-nd, 50-th, and 98-th. The power savings are zero if the predicted PRB requirement at a particular time does not fall below the capacity base station OFF threshold, along with the prediction of total PRB demand at these percentiles are higher than the max PRBs of 140, as the capacity base station cannot be switched OFF during those times. Several icons in elliptical shapes with colors blue and magenta can be seen in the bottom subplots of all 4 figures, which represents the failure of satisfying conditions 1 and 2, respectively, causing zero power saving at corresponding time stamps. Figure 6 shows the power saving achieved using the GPVAR estimator when the capacity base station off threshold

Fig. 6: Power Saving with GPVAR Estimator when Capacity Base Station OFF Threshold is 10 PRBs.

is set to 10 PRBs. The capacity base station is kept ON most of the time as conditions 1 and 2 are not always met. At the time between 17:00 to 24:00 hours and 41:00 to 48:00 hours, the total PRB demand predictions in subplot 1 shaded in coral-red at the 98-th percentile are above max 140 PRBs (condition 2 not satisfied) due to which the capacity station is kept ON as the coverage station alone cannot handle all the traffic demands. During times highlighted in a blue ellipse, like hours 1:00, 2:00, 12:00 to 25:00, and 34:00 to 48, condition 1 is not satisfied, resulting in zero power saving.

In Figure 7, the most important change compared to Figure 6 is the change in capacity base station OFF threshold to 55 PRBs. A higher threshold value leads to the capacity base station being switched off more frequently. It can be seen that the blue ellipse is smaller compared to the previous figure, as condition 1 is met most of the time. However, the maximum 140 PRBs requirement at percentile 98 is not met as GPVAR fails to capture the data calibration and trend. Selecting the capacity base station OFF threshold requires a strategic balance between ensuring quality of service during high traffic demand and maximising power savings without compromising network performance. Figure 8 shows the power saving and prediction of PRB demands using the TFT estimator with capacity base station OFF threshold set to 10 PRBs. Lower threshold implies

that the base station is OFF only if the predicted demands in subplot 1 are below the assigned thresholds. Similarly, Figure 9 shows the analysis of TFT predictions when the capacity base station OFF threshold is high (55 PRBs). When compared to the power saving with GPVAR in Figures 6 and 7 and TFT with a lower OFF threshold in Figure 8, The capacity base station is switched OFF most of the time, resulting in the highest power saving and energy efficiency. Condition 2 is fulfilled in TFT most of the time, as the predictions are better than GPVAR and they follow the trend of the true observations. Except for the times 45:00 and 46:00 hours, condition 2 is fulfilled in all other hours, regardless of the capacity station OFF threshold (i.e. both in figure 8 and in 9). The effects of the percentiles and the OFF threshold can be better understood using Table III.

Table III shows the over- and under-provisioning percentages of different forecast models for the case of predicted total PRB demands and the energy saving with various OFF thresholds achieved at different percentiles. The over and under-estimations are independent of the capacity station OFF threshold. The average energy saving per hour is high for the lower percentiles in all forecast models, but at the cost of a very high under-provisioning percentage which degrades the quality of service. Moreover, a higher base station OFF

Fig. 7: Power Saving with GPVAR Estimator when Capacity Base Station OFF Threshold is 55 PRBs.

TABLE III: Comparison of the performance of different forecast methods in terms of Energy Saving

Forecast Models		Percentiles					
		2-nd	25-th	50-th	75-th	90-th	98-th
Total PRB Demands Overprovisioning %							
LSTM		41.66					
GPVAR		2.08	37.5	64.58	91.66	91.66	100
TFT		10.41	37.5	60.57	81.25	89.58	97.91
Total PRB Demands Underprovisioning %							
LSTM		58.33					
GPVAR		97.91	62.5	35.41	8.33	8.33	0
TFT		89.58	62.5	39.43	18.75	10.41	2.08
Capacity Base Station OFF Threshold	Forecast Models	Energy Saving %					
		11.255					
10 PRBs	LSTM	11.255					
	GPVAR	23.01	21.70	21.05	15.48	14.26	13.02
	TFT	23.01	21.70	19.16	16.68	16.68	14.83
15 PRBs	LSTM	19.23					
	GPVAR	26.05	22.34	21.70	21.05	21.05	17.33
	TFT	23.77	22.34	21.70	21.05	21.05	18.54
20 PRBs	LSTM	23.79					
	GPVAR	30.50	23.01	22.34	21.70	21.70	17.33
	TFT	27.49	23.01	23.01	22.34	21.05	21.05
35 PRBs	LSTM	30.58					
	GPVAR	30.58	30.58	27.44	24.57	23.01	18.62
	TFT	30.58	29.75	28.96	23.77	23.01	23.01
55 PRBs	LSTM	30.58					
	GPVAR	30.58	30.58	30.58	30.58	30.58	22.27
	TFT	30.58	30.58	30.58	30.58	29.75	28.96

Fig. 8: Power Saving with TFT Estimator when Capacity Base Station OFF Threshold is 10 PRBs.

threshold can help achieve higher energy savings. Nevertheless, its selection should ensure that the coverage base station is not pushed into a bottleneck. Overall, it can be concluded that probabilistic models such as TFT and GPVAR represent a better compromise between under-provisioning and energy saving. This makes them more reliable and suitable for real-world applications where network performance and resource efficiency are critical. From all the above analysis, TFTs performs better in terms of key metrics such as CRPS, deviation and quantile loss due to high confidence in prediction and precise understanding of data trends, along with stable performance in terms of low over-provisioning at higher percentiles and increased energy savings.

Although the results obtained are promising, real-world deployment of the proposed framework into the O-RAN RIC environment imposes several practical challenges. Moreover, proper coordination between rApps and xApps is crucial when integrating such forecasting logic to avoid control conflicts. Additionally, ensuring computational scalability and maintaining interoperability under dynamic network conditions is also essential. Furthermore, to build a robust framework, evaluating it over extended time horizons will be crucial for assessing its long-term stability, scalability, and adaptability. Addressing these aspects would enable seamless, reliable deployment of

the proposed framework in a real-world environment.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we investigated the integration of probabilistic forecasting techniques into the O-RAN architecture to improve network analysis and resource management. The paper gives with an overview of the O-RAN framework, highlighting its components and the importance of power-efficient operation for sustainable network deployment. We addressed the limitations of traditional deterministic models in handling the dynamic and uncertain nature of modern mobile networks and proposed probabilistic forecasting as a robust alternative. Our simulation results emphasise the potential of probabilistic forecasting to significantly improve the operational efficiency and sustainability of O-RAN implementations. By incorporating these techniques into RIC, operators can achieve dynamic and adaptive resource management that improves overall network performance and reduces energy consumption. Performance analysis showed that probabilistic estimators like GPVAR and TFT more accurately predicted the PRB requirements, which in turn helped achieve power savings. Different percentiles presented more interesting results with a clear tradeoff between performance and energy saving in terms of diverse metrics. Lower percentiles showed promising results in terms

Fig. 9: Power Saving with TFT Estimator when Capacity Base Station OFF Threshold is 55 PRBs.

of reduced power wastage by saving 23.01% to 30.58% but at the cost of compromised service quality due to a high under-provisioning of 97.91% and 89.58% for GPVAR and TFT, respectively. LSTM, on the contrary, performed the worst due to its sensitivity to outliers and poor understanding of the data trends, leading to the lowest scores of MAE and MAPE of 18.01 and 79.89%, respectively, especially for the case of coverage base station resource prediction. Future work can focus on developing probabilistic forecasting techniques in a proof-of-concept implementation considering real hardware on existing platforms to test performance in real-world deployment scenarios. Moreover, the proposed probabilistic forecasting framework provides a foundational step toward practical O-RAN implementation. To enhance its real-world applicability, future work should also consider integrating uncertainties such as delays and variations in network conditions. These advancements will aid in strengthening the framework's robustness and reliability under dynamic network conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. S. Abdalla, P. S. Upadhyaya, V. K. Shah, and V. Marojevic, "Toward next generation open radio access networks: What o-ran can and cannot do!," *IEEE Network*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 206–213, 2022.
- [2] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'oro, S. Basagni, and T. Melodia, "Understanding o-ran: Architecture, interfaces, algorithms, security, and research challenges," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1376–1411, 2023.
- [3] L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, M. Polese, S. Basagni, and T. Melodia, "Intelligence and learning in o-ran for data-driven nextg cellular networks," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 59, no. 10, pp. 21–27, 2021.
- [4] V. Kasuluru, L. Blanco, and E. Zeydan, "On the use of probabilistic forecasting for network analysis in open ran," in *2023 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom)*, pp. 258–263, 2023.
- [5] V. Kasuluru, L. Blanco, E. Zeydan, A. Bel, and A. Antonopoulos, "Enhancing cloud-native resource allocation with probabilistic forecasting techniques in o-ran," in *2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, pp. 1–6, 2024.
- [6] C. Freitag, M. Berners-Lee, K. Widdicks, B. Knowles, G. S. Blair, and A. Friday, "The real climate and transformative impact of ict: a critique of estimates, trends, and regulations," *Patterns*, vol. 3, no. 8, 2022.
- [7] J. Malmodin, N. Lövehagen, P. Bergmark, and D. Lundén, "Ict sector electricity consumption and greenhouse gas emissions—2020 outcome," *Telecommunications Policy*, vol. 48, no. 3, 2024.
- [8] "Sustainability and ict - Ericsson mobility report data and forecasts." <https://www.ericsson.com/en/reports-and-papers/mobility-report/dataforecasts/ict-sustainability>. Accessed: July 30, 2024.
- [9] Enerdata, "Between 10 and 20% of electricity consumption from the ict sector in 2030?." <https://www.enerdata.net/publications/executive-briefing/world-energy-consumption-from-digitalization.pdf>, 2018. Accessed: March 2, 2024.
- [10] L. M. Larsen, H. L. Christiansen, S. Ruepp, and M. S. Berger, "Toward greener 5g and beyond radio access networks—a survey," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 4, pp. 768–797, 2023.

- [11] O-RAN Alliance, "O-RAN Working Group 1 Use Cases Detailed Specification, v09.00." October 2022.
- [12] D. López-Pérez, A. De Domenico, N. Piovesan, G. Xinli, H. Bao, S. Qitao, and M. Debbah, "A survey on 5g radio access network energy efficiency: Massive mimo, lean carrier design, sleep modes, and machine learning," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2022.
- [13] F. Han, S. Zhao, L. Zhang, and J. Wu, "Survey of strategies for switching off base stations in heterogeneous networks for greener 5g systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 4, 2016.
- [14] M. Hoffmann, P. Kryszkiewicz, and A. Kliks, "Increasing energy efficiency of massive-mimo network via base stations switching using reinforcement learning and radio environment maps," *Computer Communications*, vol. 169, 2021.
- [15] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Perez, "Deepcog: Cognitive network management in sliced 5g networks with deep learning," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2019-IEEE conference on computer communications*, IEEE, 2019.
- [16] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Perez, "Aztec: Anticipatory capacity allocation for zero-touch network slicing," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2020-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, IEEE, 2020.
- [17] N. Piovesan, D. López-Pérez, A. De Domenico, X. Geng, H. Bao, and M. Debbah, "Machine learning and analytical power consumption models for 5g base stations," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 10, pp. 56–62, 2022.
- [18] N. Piovesan, D. López-Pérez, A. De Domenico, X. Geng, and H. Bao, "Power consumption modeling of 5g multi-carrier base stations: A machine learning approach," in *ICC 2023-IEEE International Conference on Communications*, IEEE, 2023.
- [19] D. López-Pérez, A. De Domenico, N. Piovesan, and M. Debbah, "Data-driven energy efficiency modelling in large-scale networks: An expert knowledge and ml-based approach," *IEEE Transactions on Machine Learning in Communications and Networking*, 2024.
- [20] Y. Zhang, J. Wang, and X. Wang, "Review on probabilistic forecasting of wind power generation," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 32, pp. 255–270, 2014.
- [21] E. Spiliotis, S. Makridakis, A. Kaltsounis, and V. Assimakopoulos, "Product sales probabilistic forecasting: An empirical evaluation using the m5 competition data," *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 240, p. 108237, 2021.
- [22] W. Wang, C. Zhou, H. He, W. Wu, W. Zhuang, and X. Shen, "Cellular traffic load prediction with lstm and gaussian process regression," in *ICC 2020-2020 IEEE international conference on communications (ICC)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2020.
- [23] W. Benrhaim and A. S. Hafid, "Bayesian networks based reliable broadcast in vehicular networks," *Vehicular Communications*, vol. 21, p. 100181, 2020.
- [24] K. Chen, Q. Kong, Y. Dai, Y. Xu, F. Yin, L. Xu, and S. Cui, "Recent advances in data-driven wireless communication using gaussian processes: a comprehensive survey," *China Communications*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 218–237, 2022.
- [25] M. Li, Y. Wang, Z. Wang, and H. Zheng, "A deep learning method based on an attention mechanism for wireless network traffic prediction," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 107, p. 102258, 2020.
- [26] O-RAN Alliance, "O-ran use cases and deployment scenarios whitepaper." <https://www.o-ran.org/resources>, Feb 2020. Accessed: 2023-12-05.
- [27] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, S. Basagni, and T. Melodia, "Understanding o-ran: Architecture, interfaces, algorithms, security, and research challenges," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1376–1411, 2023.
- [28] V. Kasuluru, L. Blanco, C. J. Vaca-Rubio, and E. Zeydan, "On the impact of prb load uncertainty forecasting for sustainable open ran," 2024.
- [29] M. Hoffmann *et al.*, "Open ran xapps design and evaluation: Lessons learnt and identified challenges," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 473–486, 2024.
- [30] T. Song, D. Lopez, M. Meo, N. Piovesan, and D. Renga, "High altitude platform stations: the new network energy efficiency enabler in the 6g era," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.00969*, 2023.
- [31] V. Kasuluru, L. Blanco, and E. Zeydan, "Enhancing open ran operations: The role of probabilistic forecasting in network analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 2025.
- [32] D. Salinas, M. Bohlke-Schneider, L. Callot, R. Medico, and J. Gasthaus, "High-dimensional multivariate forecasting with low-rank gaussian copula processes," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [33] B. Lim, S. Ö. Arık, N. Loeff, and T. Pfister, "Temporal fusion transformers for interpretable multi-horizon time series forecasting," *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 1748–1764, 2021.
- [34] A. Sherstinsky, "Fundamentals of recurrent neural network (rnn) and long short-term memory (lstm) network," *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, vol. 404, p. 132306, 2020.
- [35] G. Elidan, "Copulas in machine learning," in *Copulae in Mathematical and Quantitative Finance: Proceedings of the Workshop Held in Cracow, 10-11 July 2012*, pp. 39–60, Springer, 2013.
- [36] D. Salinas, V. Flunkert, J. Gasthaus, and T. Januschowski, "Deepar: Probabilistic forecasting with autoregressive recurrent networks," *International journal of forecasting*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 1181–1191, 2020.
- [37] H. Wen, J. Gu, J. Ma, L. Yuan, and Z. Jin, "Probabilistic load forecasting via neural basis expansion model based prediction intervals," *IEEE transactions on smart grid*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 3648–3660, 2021.
- [38] J. Berrisch and F. Ziel, "Multivariate probabilistic crps learning with an application to day-ahead electricity prices," *International Journal of Forecasting*, 2024.
- [39] F. Rezazadeh, L. Zanzi, F. Devoti, H. Chergui, X. Costa-Perez, and C. Verikoukis, "On the specialization of fdr agents for scalable and distributed 6g ran slicing orchestration," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 3, pp. 3473–3487, 2022.

Vaishnavi Kasuluru completed her M.Sc. degree in Information and Communication Engineering from TU Darmstadt, Germany in 2020 and her B.Sc. degree in Electronics and Communication Engineering from SSN College of Engineering, affiliated with Anna University, Chennai, India in 2016. Currently, she is working as a researcher at the SRCOM Research Unit in CTTC, Barcelona, Spain, where she is also pursuing her PhD and is involved in an EU-funded project called SEMANTIC. Her research interests include developing Optimization and Machine Learning algorithms to solve challenging real-world Telecommunication problems.

Luis Blanco received his MSc and PhD in Telecommunications engineering from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC), Spain, in 2006 and 2017, respectively. He holds a MSc degree in Research on Information and Communications Technologies (MERIT) from the UPC since 2012. In addition, Dr. Blanco holds an MBA from IDE-CESEM, Instituto de Directivos de Empresa (Madrid). In 2007, he joined the Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), where he currently holds a position as a senior researcher. Dr. Blanco has actively participated in more than 20 research projects funded by public and private entities, including EC-funded projects, national projects and industrial projects with top-tier international companies. He has been the Project Manager (2020-2021) and Coordinator (2021-2022) of the MSCA-ITN SEMANTIC and has led different projects with European industry. Currently, Dr. Blanco is the Scientific Manager of the HE-SNS project UNITY-6G and leads the AI-based RIC activities in 5G-STARBUCK. His primary research areas of interest include optimization and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for wireless communication systems in beyond 5G and 6G integrated networks.

Cristian J. Vaca-Rubio (Member, IEEE) is currently a Researcher at the Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC) in Barcelona, Spain. He received the Telematics engineering degree, and the master's degree in Telematics and Telecommunication Networks from University of Malaga (UMA), Malaga, Spain, in 2018, and 2019, respectively. He received the Ph.D. degree in Wireless Communications from Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark in 2023. In parallel to his telematics and master studies, he worked as a research

assistant with the Communication Engineering Department at University of Malaga from February 2018 until July 2019 in a joint project with DEKRA GmbH. He pursued the Ph.D. degree with the Connectivity Section, Electronic Systems Department, Aalborg University, under a Marie Curie Fellowship as an Early Stage Researcher (ESR) in the H2020 ITN Wind Mill Project, where he joined in September 2019. During his Ph.D., he was a visiting researcher at Mitsubishi Electric Research Laboratories (MERL), Cambridge, USA for a period of 9 months. His main research activities are in wireless communications and sensing, machine learning, massive MIMO, mobile networks, telematics, and applied statistics in video streaming. He received the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing top 3% paper award in 2023. He is also the author of a submitted patent along with MERL co-authors.

Engin Zeydan received his Ph.D. degree in February 2011 from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at Stevens Institute of Technology, Hoboken, NJ, USA. He is currently a Senior Researcher at Services as Networks (SaS) Research Unit in CTTC, Barcelona, Spain. He is currently the Project Coordinator of the Horizon Europe UNITY-6G European Project (January 2025-December 2027). He was the Project Coordinator of the Horizon 2020 MonB5G European Project (November 2021-April 2023). His research interests

are in the areas of telecommunications, data engineering and network security.

Albert Bel received his BSc degree in telecommunications engineering (2007), the MSc degree in micro and nanotechnologies (2008) and the Ph.D. degree in telecommunications and systems engineering (2012) from the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB). From 2013 until 2022 he holds a Lecturer position at the engineering department at the Universitat Pompeu Fabra where has been involved in several international and national research projects and coordinating two undergraduate subjects. In 2023, he joined the Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions

de Catalunya (CTTC) as a researcher at the Services as Networks (SaS) research unit. His research interests are in the area of Open RAN, optimization of 5G and 6G networks, mostly focused on the testbed implementations.